

A COMPARATIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE AMONG PARENTS REGARDING EARLY DETECTION OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY IN RURAL AND URBAN AREAS OF WEST BENGAL, INDIA

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Abstract:

Introduction: Delinquency is unwelcomed action, omission or moral behavior of a juvenile, which is socially not permitted in any society. Generally it means that if the child fails to meet certain social obligations anticipated from them by the Standards and Goals made by the society. **Aim:** to assess the knowledge and attitude among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas. **Materials and Methods:** A quantitative non experimental research approach, comparative research design was used. Total samples were 1000 parents (500 in rural and 500 in urban areas) of West Bengal were selected by non probability purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by using self structured knowledge questionnaire and self structured attitude scale. **Results:** The study results depicted that the parents in urban areas have more average knowledge and negative attitude than rural areas regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency. **Conclusion:** the study concluded that parents in urban areas have more knowledge and negative attitude than parents in rural areas.

Keywords: early detection of Juvenile delinquency, Parents.

Introduction:

“Children must be taught what to think, not what to think.”

Margaret Mead

Juvenile Delinquency is an unwelcomed action, omission or moral behavior of a juvenile, which is socially not permitted in any society. Generally in it the child fails to meet certain social obligations anticipated in the society. The juvenile delinquent is behavioral disorder which is generally defined as “a child trying or pretending to act like a grown up or adult”. The action of the child can be seen as a childish foolish behavior but it can cause serious worry and concern. There is a narrow difference between a delinquent child and a normal child and the behavior of an anxious person is the deciding factor among a cheerful act and delinquency.¹ The cases registered under various sections of IPC crimes against juveniles in conflict with law in 2014 have increased by 5.7% over 2013 as 31,725 cases against juveniles were registered under IPC crimes during 2013 which increased to a total number of 33,526 such cases in 2014. The highest number of cases registered against juveniles were reported under the crime head which included theft“ (20.0%), rape“ (5.9%) and „grievous hurt“ & 'assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty' (4,7% each). The incidence is increasing worldwide and in India, the majority of the crime was done by youths who are in the age group of 15-18 years. Recently crime rate against females are increasing.² In India juvenile delinquency was increased in the year 1995 the crime rate was 9766, in short duration of 6 years crime rate increased to 16,509 and during 2005 its number is again been raised to 18, 939. The concept of juvenile delinquency is much complied and varies from country to country and even in the various provinces of the same country. There is no definition that may be used worldwide because the sociologists, psychologists and legalists define ‘Juvenile Delinquency’ in their own way. It varies from nation to nation, for what is forbidden to do at one place, can be allowed in the other place.

Objectives

1. To assess the knowledge regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas.
2. To assess the attitude regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas.

3. To compare the knowledge and attitude regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas
4. To find out the association of knowledge score among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas with demographic variables.
5. To find out the association of attitude score among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas with demographic variables.

Materials and Methods

Research approach and design

A quantitative Non experimental research approach, comparative research design was considered to be the most appropriate.

Variables of the study

Research Variable: Juvenile delinquency

Demographic variable: knowledge and attitude of parents

Research Setting

The setting for the present study was in rural and urban areas, West Bengal.

Rural Area of West Bengal including District:- Purba Bardhaman

Urban Area of West Bengal including District:- Paschim Bardhaman

The selection of this areas were done on the basis of geographical proximity, feasibility of conducting the study, economy in terms of time, easy transport facilities and availability of sample.

Target Population

The target population for study was the parents of West Bengal

Sample size and Sampling Technique:

The total sample size for the study comprises of 1000 parents i.e. 500 in rural area and 500 in urban area of West Bengal. Non probability purposive sampling technique was used for sampling.

Inclusion criteria

1. Parents of children 6-18 years.
2. Sample size 1000 parents. 500 in rural and 500 in urban area
3. Parents who will be present at the time of data collection.
4. Parents who will be willing to participate at the time of data collection.

Exclusion criteria

1. Absent at the time of data collection.
2. Not willing to participate.

Selection and development of tool:

A Self structured knowledge questionnaire and Self structured attitude scale was prepared for assessing the knowledge and attitude of Parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency.

It was divided into three sections:

Part A: Structured demographic sheet

Part B: Self Structured Knowledge Questionnaire

It comprised of 30 multiple choice questions with every correct answer was awarded as ‘one’ and incorrect answer ‘zero’.

Criterion measurement for knowledge:

S.No	Criterion measurement	Score
1.	Good	21-30
2	Average	11-20
3	Below average	0-10

Part C: Self Structured Attitude Scale

It comprised of 30 questions in Likert scale form having 4 options that are given as follows: strongly disagree = 1, disagree = 2, agree = 3, strongly agree = 4. lowest score is 30 and highest is 120.

Criterion for attitude measurement:

S.No.	Criterion Measurement	Score
1.	Positive attitude	91-120
2	Negative attitude	61-90
3.	Nullified attitude	30-60

Data Analysis

Data analysis was based on the objectives stated in the study by using descriptive and inferential statistics by calculating the frequency, percentage, t-test, ANOVA. Bar graphs were used for pictorial presentation.

Results

The sample characteristics: in relation to **age** , it was found that in rural area maximum were in the age group of 26-30 years (38%), followed by 31-35 years (34%), 21-25 years (22%) and above 36 years (6%); where as in urban area maximum were in age group of 31-35 years (38%), followed by 26-30 years (36%), 21-25 years (20%) and above 36 years (6%). In relation to **gender** the percentage distribution of parents in both rural and urban areas were found that maximum were females (70% and 68%) followed by males (30% and 32%). While as per percentage distribution of parents according to **religion**, it was found that maximum were in (62%) Hindu, followed by (35%) Sikh , followed by (3%) Muslim and followed by Christian (0%). With relation to **Education qualification** the percentage distribution of parents was found that in rural area Majority were higher secondary passed (77%) followed by secondary (14%), graduate (8%); whereas the percentage distribution of parents in urban area was found that majority were graduates (63%), followed by Secondary (12%), higher secondary (19%), Post graduate (6%). As per **Employment status** the percentage distribution of parents was found that majority were farmer (83%), followed by private sector (8%), Govt. sector (7%) and unemployed (2%); where as in Urban area the majority were found working in Private sector (68%), followed by Farmer (25%), Govt. sector (7%) and unemployed (0%). As per **Area of residence** the percentage distribution of rural areas were 100% and the percentage distribution of urban areas were 100%. According to **type of family** the percentage distribution shows that majority of parents in rural and urban areas were living in nuclear family (55% and 65%), followed by joint family (45% and 35%). With respect to **Sources of information about juvenile delinquency** the percentage distribution was found that in both rural and urban areas majority were found to be from social media(43%), followed by television (29%), friends and family (16%), news paper (11%). As per **child tendency of absenteeism** the percentage distribution in rural areas was found that for Yes it was 34% and for No 66%; where as in urban areas the percentage distribution for Yes was 23% and for No 77%.

Findings as per the objectives of the study:

Objective 1: To assess the knowledge regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas.

The study represents the knowledge score of parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency. Here, the parents in both rural and urban areas have Average knowledge regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency (72% in rural areas and 76% in urban areas) followed by good (2.8% in rural areas and 1.8% in urban areas); below average (25.2% in rural areas and 22.2% in urban areas). This result is supported by the study done by Sarah BD (2009),⁵ the findings strongly support that the population have less knowledge regarding juvenile delinquency and have negative attitude towards it.

Criteria Measure of Knowledge Score N=1000 (Rural= 500, Urban= 500)					
CATEGORY	SCORE	RURAL (f)	RURAL (%)	URBAN (f)	URBAN (%)
GOOD	(21-30)	14	2.8%	9	1.8%
AVERAGE	(11-20)	360	72%	380	76%
BELOW AVERAGE	(0-10)	126	25.2%	111	22.2%

Table 2 represents the knowledge regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among the parents in rural areas and urban areas.

Objective 2: To assess the attitude regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas.

The study represents the attitude score regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among the parents in rural areas and urban areas. Here it is found that the parents in both rural areas and urban areas had Negative attitude i.e., 75.4 % in rural area and 77.2 % in urban areas regarding juvenile delinquency, followed by positive attitude 24.6% in rural areas and 22.8% in urban areas. The was supported by the study of Celeste simões (2013)⁷ was conducted the descriptive study on attitude of parents regarding juvenile delinquent behavior in higher secondary students. Samples were 200 parents of higher secondary students. The result showed that 57% of the parents had negative attitude toward juvenile delinquent behavior, 33% of the parents agree that juvenile delinquent behavior can be manageable if taken under consideration, 10% had no comments juvenile delinquent behavior.

Criteria Measure Of Attitude Score N=1000 (Rural= 500, Urban= 500)					
Category	Score	Rural (f)	Rural (%)	Urban (f)	Urban (%)
Positive Attitude	91-120	123	24.6%	114	22.8%
Negative Attitude	61-90	377	75.4%	386	77.2%
Neutral Attitude	30-60	0	0%	0	0%

Table 3 represents the attitude regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas.

Objective 3: To compare the knowledge and attitude regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency among parents of rural and urban areas

The study represents the comparison of knowledge score in rural and urban areas. In rural area the mean±S.D. is 12.79±3.527 and in urban area the mean±S.D. is 12.87±3.151, these both results are non significant at significance

level of 0.05. Whereas the comparison of attitude score in rural and urban areas represents that in rural areas the mean±S.D. is 86.97±5.885 which is more than in urban area mean±S.D. is 86.91±5.755, these both results are non significant at significance level of 0.05. It is supported by the study done by Okon (2016)⁶, the majority held awareness regarding juvenile delinquents.

N= 500

Unpaired T Test		Mean Score	S.D.	N	Mean F	Unpaired Test	P value	Table Value at 0.05	Result
Knowledge Score	Rural	12.79	3.527	500	42.63	0.359	0.719	1.962	Non Significant
	Urban	12.87	3.151	500	42.89				

Maximum =30 Minimum= 0

p<0.05 level of significance

Table 4 represents the comparison of knowledge score in rural and urban areas.

Unpaired T Test		Mean Score	S.D.	N	Unpaired Test	P value	Table Value at 0.05	Result
Attitude Score	Rural	86.97	5.885	500	0.158	0.875	1.962	Non Significant
	Urban	86.91	5.755	500				

Maximum =120 Minimum=30

p<0.05 level of significance

Table 5 represents the comparison of attitude score among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas with demographic variables.

Objective 4: To find out the association of knowledge score among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas with demographic variables.

In rural areas there was significant association with religion, as statistically analyzed with ANOVA test, $F=3.113^*$ and type of family as statistically analyzed with ANNOVA test, $F= 4.235^*$. But there was no significant association between knowledge score with age, gender, qualification, employment status, area of residence, source of information, child tendency of absenteeism. In urban areas there was significant association with source of information, as statistically analyzed with ANOVA test, $F=3.113^*$ and type of family as statistically analyzed with ANNOVA test, $F= 4.23^*$. But there was no significant association between knowledge score with age, gender, religion, qualification, employment status, area of residence, child tendency of absenteeism. It is supported by the study done by Lahey BB (2012).⁸ This suggests that the association between parental knowledge and future delinquency is not solely spurious; rather parental knowledge and limit setting are both meaningful predictors of future delinquency.

Objective 5: To find out the association of attitude score among parents regarding early detection of juvenile delinquency in rural and urban areas with demographic variables.

In rural areas there was no significant association between attitude score with age, gender, religion, qualification employment status, area of residence, type of family, source of information and child tendency of absenteeism at 0.05 level of significance. In urban areas there was no significant association between attitude score with age, gender, religion, qualification employment status, area of residence, type of family, source of information and child tendency of absenteeism at 0.05 level of significance. It is supported by the study done by Miners MH, Munns R (2011).⁹ The results indicate no association between the socio demographic variables the attitude scale.

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